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Parched Fields, Empty Plates: Investigating the Interconnected Factors Influencing Agriculture Value- Added amid Water Scarcity in Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

The water crisis poses a significant threat to agriculture, as it is essential for the survival of all plants and animals. Without an adequate supply of water, plants and livestock will perish, leading to a disruption in the process of photosynthesis and resulting in a lack of food for our population. Furthermore, agriculture plays a vital role in economic growth, accounting for 4% of the world's gross domestic product and providing a source of income for many of the poorest individuals in developing nations. In Pakistan, water scarcity has had a detrimental effect on food availability. This study aims to examine the impact of water scarcity on food availability in Pakistan using time series data from 1990 to 2022. The study employs the ARDL model to investigate the short-term and long-term effects of water scarcity on agriculture value-added, as well as the effects of rainfall, rural unemployment, rural poverty, agriculture mechanization, and extreme temperature on agriculture value-added. The results indicate that water scarcity has a long-term negative impact on agriculture value-added, while rainfall has a negative impact on agriculture value-added in the short-term. Additionally, the study finds that agriculture mechanization and rural poverty have a negative impact on agriculture value-added. These findings have important implications for the development of policy guidelines aimed at addressing water scarcity and food insecurity caused by water scarcity and other factors.

Keywords: Water scarcity; Agriculture value added; Extreme temperature; Rural poverty; Rural unemployment; Agriculture mechanization; ARDL estimator; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Asian countries have made great strides toward greater food security and agricultural growth during the previous half-century. In spite of their massive populations, countries like China and India are no longer dependent on foreign food aid since they can provide for themselves. Nutritional initiatives focusing on the needs of local communities have been particularly successful in Indonesia and Thailand, and are thus frequently held up as examples for other developing nations. The phrase "basket case" is no longer used to describe developing nations like Bangladesh or India. The possibilities for ending hunger have been substantially enhanced by the establishment of peace in Cambodia and East Timor (Berno et al., 2020).

Pakistan's rural regions rely heavily on the agricultural industry for economic development, food security, job creation, and poverty alleviation. Over 65–70% of the population depends on agriculture for their living, and the sector contributes 19.2% to GDP while employing 38.5% of the labour force. However, challenges have arisen for the industry as a whole due to phenomena including declining arable land, climate change, water shortages, and the movement of people from rural to urban regions. New strategies need to be used in agriculture if production is to rise. According to Yaqoob et al. (2023), a 1% rise in per-capita agricultural growth leads to a 1.5% increase in per-capita non-agricultural growth, demonstrating the beneficial effect of a thriving agricultural sector on the economy as a whole. The agriculture sector is also affected by environmental concerns such as CO₂ emissions, which have negative impacts on human health and agricultural productivity, as reported by KarimiAlavijeh et al. (2023). The sector also contributes to roughly 11% of global greenhouse gas emissions, as per Gallagher et al. (2023), and is particularly susceptible to climate change in developing economies. Meeting future commitments under the Paris Agreement to reduce GHG emissions while maintaining agricultural growth is a cause for concern, as reported by Raihan (2023). The importance of food security is increasing each year, as the safety of food raw materials and food products is one of the most important factors affecting human health and the preservation of the gene pool. Food safety refers to the absence of risk in terms of both immediate harmful effects on human health (food poisoning and food infections) and long-term implications. In other words, food products that do not harm the health of current or future generations are considered safe. Many potentially harmful compounds can enter the human body through food. As a result, significant issues are associated with increased responsibility for the effectiveness and objectivity of food quality control, and ensuring consumer protection (Umarjonovna et al., 2022). Inadequate post-harvest handling, supply chain, transportation, and weather management owing to a lack of suitable logistical infrastructure and perishables care expertise account for the vast majority of food losses, especially in developing countries (Kumar and Agrawal, 2023).

With the global population projected to exceed 9.7 billion by 2050, or 20.6% of the present population, food safety is becoming an increasingly pressing issue worldwide. However, due to certain characteristics such as soil quality, weather, topography, and significant diversity in homogenous land, not all of the planet's land is arable. Additionally, due to pollutants, soil depletion, and land degradation, the rate at which arable land is diminishing outpaces the rate at which it is recovering. All of these issues are pushing agriculture closer to being adopted and developed. In Pakistan, which is a country with an agricultural economy, 38.5% of the labor force is employed in the sector, which also accounts for 19.5% of the country's GDP (Qureshi et al., 2022). The development, consumption, and growth patterns of humans are closely tied to climate change. It has an impact on all areas surrounding the zone, with the Mediterranean experiencing the greatest impact, as stated in the International Panel on Climate Change's most recent report. Human health, natural remedies, and agricultural production are all at risk due to the incessant increase in global population. The increasing need for food leads to extensive agricultural techniques, which in turn increase the need for fertilizers and water. This strain on resources of land and water leads to soil erosion and pollution (Wang & Azam, 2024). The complex challenges posed by global environmental change to people's health and livelihoods are real, and one of the key conduits for this concern is food security. Warming temperatures, variable precipitation, ocean acidification, droughts, and flooding are all linked in studies on climate change sensitivity to food insecurity and the failure of food systems. The increasing acidity of land and water, however, is another environmental issue that has received far less attention yet has the potential to have severe, silent repercussions on the production of food (Lam et al., 2022). There is a clear correlation between access to safe water and GDP per capita. Researchers have examined the effects of climate change, water scarcity, and population growth on this relationship. In order to address these issues and promote sustainable economic development, it is essential to take a comprehensive approach that addresses the root causes of water scarcity and implements effective solutions (Mahato et al., 2022).

The enhancement of agricultural labor productivity plays a vital role in safeguarding sustainable food supplies and reducing rural poverty. In nations where agriculture is extensive, the mechanization of farming techniques is more advanced. This approach, however, can lead to small and marginal countries scaling up their agriculture rather than utilizing scale-appropriate automation with limited agricultural equipment on small-scale farmland (Vemireddy & Choudhary, 2021). In Baluchistan, Pakistan, the effects of climate change on food crops are particularly pronounced, and it is feared that these effects will become increasingly severe over time. Despite the efforts of researchers to understand the relationship between climate change and food security domestically and globally, there is still a lack of research on the environmental changes and their threats to food security in Baluchistan. Factors such as human activities, community development, economic development, and environmental changes are closely related to weather phenomena. Additionally, climate and environmental events, such as drought, aridity, disasters, and hydrological infrastructure, have significant implications for food security and human welfare in the Baluchistan province (Khan et al., 2022). Mechanized agricultural methods have been a game-changer for food production throughout the globe, helping it to keep up with the expanding human population, especially in emerging regions like Asia. China's agricultural sector is vital, contributing 7.65% to GDP in 2015 and projected to expand by 10.33% by 2020. Chinese agricultural output is characterized by its small farms and widespread land fragmentation. In the United States, small farms make up the overwhelming majority (98%) of all farms (Huan, et al., 2022). Vegetable production is essential due to its high dietary value, potential yield, profitability, and suitability for small landholding growers, as well as the high employment opportunities it offers. However, with the increasing population, the demand for food, particularly vegetables, is rising while the area under cultivation of vegetables is not increasing. Therefore, the world, particularly Asia, needs to increase food production despite land degradation and water shortages. In Pakistan, Punjab has the largest area (51.67%) under vegetable cultivation and the highest production, followed by Sindh (26.17%), Baluchistan (11.30%), and KPK (10.86%), as shown in (Riaz et al., 2022). About half of the world's population relies on rice for food, and this industry generates one billion tonnes of straw waste every year. Most farmers still choose to burn the straw before planting the following crop since they don't have much time and it's cheaper and simpler to handle, resulting in less weeds in the plants that will grow from the straw. This is despite the well-documented harmful impacts of burning on the environment, human health, and soil quality. Since combine harvesters lowered the amount of manpower needed to harvest rice, the inequitable distribution of straw, which increases the cost of collection for the farmer, is likely to have decreased (Korav et al., 2022).

In Pakistan, which is the 6th most populous country in the world with 64% of its population living in rural areas, the performance of government sectors in providing technical and financial aid against pests such as locust attacks in various districts of Baluchistan, Sindh, and Punjab provinces is unsatisfactory. As a result, declining agricultural growth is a major challenge for overall economic growth. The agricultural performance of Pakistan primarily relies on the province of Punjab, which has a lion's share of major food crops. Despite advancements in farming techniques and mechanization, crop yields have not yet significantly increased (Akhtar et al., 2022). The yields of staple crops including wheat, rice, maize, and soybeans have grown by an average of 1%-2% over the last several years thanks to technical developments and the expanding worldwide need for food and feed. To provide for the world's growing population in 2050, agricultural output per hectare of farmland may need to rise by as much as 2.4% annually, according to projections. This is because expanding the area of the world's cropland and increasing the frequency of extraction are not feasible. The areas where agricultural production has been stagnant have contributed to the slow-moving upward trend in crop yields seen over the past few decades (Rietra et al., 2022). The Ministry of Agriculture in Pakistan offers assistance to farmer organizations for the acquisition of equipment and tools to accelerate agricultural mechanization, as well as for financial support to establish farmer-owned and independent, competitive enterprise units. Mechanization has the advantage of addressing labor shortages, increasing agricultural productivity and counteracting the negative effects of climate change (Aryal et al., 2020). However, it should be noted that mechanization also increases productivity through labor substitution, but can have a negative impact on farmers who lack capital equipment. To mitigate potential negative consequences, agricultural mechanization should take into account economic, agro-climatic and social factors. However, the government does not regulate how machinery assistance is provided and managed (Hanggana et al., 2022). The world trade is focused on a few commodities, such as rice, rice products, and leather products, which make up more than 70% of all shipments (Govt. of Pakistan, 2020). The growth performance of Pakistan's key crops has been markedly slow and skewed in recent years. Not only may the distorted average productivity of fundamental plants lower domestic revenue and employment, but it can also worsen the performance of related production industries along with the growing food insecurity issue. Crop manufacturing could be very touchy to climatic adjustments related with increasing temperature, changing styles of rainfall, and excessive climate activities (Abbas, 2022).

The policy for agricultural development in Pakistan aims to achieve a breakthrough in agricultural production as an effective approach to minimize reliance on food imports and to raise the living standards of people involved in agricultural activity. As in other countries, Pakistan has chosen industrialization as the best path to economic prosperity. However, numerous natural and man-made disasters, such as floods, earthquakes, droughts, and landslides, are having a significant negative impact on agricultural growth worldwide. Agriculture employs a large part of the labor force and domestic investment has a significant impact on the economy. Therefore, it is important to respect domestic investment at the national level and to invest in new projects related to economic interest for the production of products and services in industries and agriculture (Shehreen, 2022). Globally, agriculture is shifting to new production paradigms. Due to some limitations, agriculture is subject to its unpredictable nature. The availability of valuable resources and economic rewards pose a risk to nations that rely heavily on agriculture. The issues facing Pakistan's agricultural economy include changes in weather, traditional farming practices, water shortages, fragmented land ownership, unsustainable agricultural techniques, and more. Groundwater is a major component of irrigated agriculture in Pakistan, and more than 95% of it is extracted for irrigation. The only accelerator for agricultural output is thought to be irrigation (Imran et al., 2022). Since non-agricultural growth rates rise by 1.5% for every 1% increase in agricultural growth rates, a healthy agricultural sector is crucial to the expansion of the economy as a whole. Population expansion, urbanization, industrialization, and infrastructure development have all contributed to a decrease in the availability of undeveloped land in South Asia, reinforcing the initial conceptual framework of rising agricultural land consumption on tiny plots (Yaqoob et al., 2023). Many sectors, including farming, are already feeling the effects of climate change. Food security, biodiversity, and livelihoods continue to be threatened as a result of this phenomenon. Many social, ecological, climatic, and market-related vulnerabilities affect the agricultural practices of people in poor nations like Pakistan, where weather changes have a negative effect on crop productivity (Sargani et al., 2023).

1.1. Research Gap(s)

Previous studies have identified various factors contributing to Pakistan's water deficit, such as the relationship between physical and biological water scarcity and the impact of urbanization on human-induced water scarcity. Global urban population growth and water scarcity have also been studied. Research has also been conducted on water resources management, limited water productivity in the agricultural sector, agricultural production structure, virtual water exports, and water loss in the route, water consumption. The impact of water shortages on food availability in Pakistan has been examined previously, as well as the effect of mechanized agriculture on climate change rural poverty, unemployment, and the effect of agriculture mechanization on rural unemployment. However, this study specifically examines the effects of water constraint on food supply in Pakistan and the value given to agriculture by various factors.

1.2. Research Questions

The study aims to answer the following research question: *"Does climate risk increase food security challenges in Pakistan?"* Previous studies have examined the impact of water crisis on Pakistan's food supply (Akbar et al., 2021), the effects of mechanized agriculture on climate change (Belton et al., 2021). However, this study is unique in that it aims to investigate the relationship between climate risk and food security challenges in Pakistan in more depth by adding agriculture mechanization and climate risk factors. The second research question of the study is: *"Does low yields of grain production and low technology adaptation in the agriculture sector increase food security challenges in Pakistan?"* This question aims to investigate the relationship between grain production yields and technology adoption in the agriculture sector and the challenges they pose to food security in Pakistan. The study will likely examine data and research on the current state of grain production and technology adoption in the agriculture sector in Pakistan and how they may contribute to food security challenges in the country. Achieving SDG1 and SDG2, i.e., to reduce poverty and hunger requires sustained advances in agricultural manufacturing in developing countries, notably in South Asia and Africa. The third research question of the

study is: *"How does the availability of food protection relate to the focus on improving the efficiency and sustainability of agriculture production?"* This question aims to investigate the relationship between the availability of food protection and the efforts to improve the efficiency and sustainability of agriculture production. The fourth research question of the study is: *"Does rural poverty, unskilled labor, and high transportation cost increase food challenges in Pakistan?"* This question aims to investigate the relationship between rural poverty, unskilled labor, and high transportation cost, and the challenges they pose to food security in Pakistan. The study will likely examine data and research on the current state of rural poverty, unskilled labor, and transportation cost in Pakistan and how they may contribute to food security challenges in the country.

1.3. Objectives of the Study

The first research objective of the study is to analyze the impact of climate risk vulnerability on agriculture production in Pakistan. This objective aims to investigate the relationship between climate risk and its effect on agricultural production in Pakistan, and how it may contribute to food security challenges in the country. The second research objective is to evaluate the role of agriculture mechanisms on agricultural production in Pakistan. This objective aims to investigate the relationship between the use of agricultural mechanisms and their effect on agricultural production in Pakistan, and how they may contribute to food security challenges in the country. The third research objective is to examine the socio-economic causes and their consequence on agricultural production in Pakistan. This objective aims to investigate the relationship between socio-economic factors such as poverty, unemployment, and transportation cost and their effect on agricultural production in Pakistan, and how they may contribute to food security challenges in the country.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The study by Falcon et al. (1966) found that the growth in West Pakistan agriculture was a key aspect of the overall national agricultural performance. Between the years 1947/48 to 1958/59, there were significant year-to-year fluctuations, but few of the major crops showed significant increases. However, a sudden upturn did occur in the period of 1959/60 to 1964/65. Due to their growth and absolute level of significance, and also because the data is much more reliable, the period of 1960/61 to 1964/65, the agricultural picture changed significantly. The annual agricultural growth rate almost tripled, rising from 1.2 to 3.2 percent, agricultural exports improved swiftly. (Ahungwa et al., 2014) examined the pattern and the impact of agriculture on Nigeria's GDP over a period of 53 years (1960-2012). Regression analysis and trend were used to analyze time-series data. The findings showed that, from 1960 to 1975, agriculture's share of the total GDP decreased while clearly dominating other industries. Further analysis revealed an undulating pattern that from 1976 to 1989 intertwined with the industrial sector. The study subsequently advised the government to develop a permissive environment by increasing financial allocation and strengthening the regulatory framework and efficient agricultural sector that can accelerate. Vasile et al. (2017) aimed to examine how domestic financial policy laws have changed the Romanian agriculture paradigm. A method of econometric analysis was used to examine the changes in Romanian agriculture between 1960 and 2011 in terms of how they may have affected the economy for residential land. This methodological decision was supported by its wide range of applicability and ability to reveal the significant development of the Romanian agricultural paradigm over the time period in question. In order to study the evolution of total cost introduced and labor productivity in agriculture, two regression models were established. Alston (1979) examined the impact of late-season foliar fertilization with nitrogen and phosphorus on wheat yield and composition. To determine potential impacts of soil water stress on conelet production the following spring, 40 loblolly pine remits were exposed to mixtures of irrigation and dryness interventions during the 1967 growing season. The trees that received irrigation from April to June followed by a drought from July to September produced a much greater conelet yield compared to the other treatments. The findings imply that irrigation may reduce cone production during late summer dry spells. Fitzgerald & Parai (1996) analyzed the Green Revolution as a technical response to the severe global food shortage that emerged in the years following World War II. Although the primary food crops of maize and wheat were grown in many tropical and subtropical regions thanks to the Green Revolution, the Indian subcontinent will be the focus of the brief story that follows. In this case, the ambiguity that characterizes all eras is shown by the undesirable ecological repercussions, which are widely recorded, and by the socioeconomic consequences, which may be the subject of less agreement. India's agricultural output declined from the time of its independence in 1947 until 1965, when it became unable to meet the demands of the nation. Severe droughts inside the mid-1960s threatened famine which was avoided only through full-size shipments of food grains from the USA.

Evenson et al. (2003) summarized the findings of a recent study on the productivity implications of worldwide crop genetic improvement efforts in developing nations. International agricultural research institutions collaborated with national research initiatives from 1960 to 2000 to develop "modern varieties" for a range of crops. These cultivars have significantly enhanced crop production. However, gains in productivity have not been uniform among crops or geographic regions, and typically, consumers have benefited from decreases in food prices while farmers only profited when price reductions resulted in cost reductions. Using Arrighi's theory of capital accumulation cycles, Patel (2013) research looks into the mechanics of the Green Revolution and argues that a Long Green Revolution spanning the twentieth and twenty-first century may be identified. Similarities between the causes of past and present Green Revolutions, such as hegemonic struggles and accumulation crises, modes of governance, especially the ties between government and philanthropic institutions, and the establishment of agricultural exchange truths, are revealed by such an examination. Comparative research shows parallels between the original Green Transformation and the 21st-century agricultural revolution. It was discovered by Ozdemir (2022) that although emerging countries place equivalent importance on short-term worries to the security of the global food supply, climate change is having serious effects on farmland or may require constant modelling. Long-term relationships between agricultural output and other climatic variables were found, while a correlation between agricultural output and CO₂ pollution was found only in the short term. Furthermore, carbon enrichment in the environment can, up to a point, have a positive influence on farming output, despite the fact that this effect is initially positive and then goes negative. It is important to remember, however, that CO₂ emissions have a detrimental long-

term impact on agricultural output, and that policy and decision-makers should bear this in mind when developing policies and strategies pertaining to agriculture and climate change. Shu et al. (2021) studied water stress directories, which were designed to define different types of water stress and control the region's water scarcity. China, in particular, is facing severe water stress due to a shortage of water resources in the northwest and northeast regions. The created blue, green, and grey water shortage directories make up for the current index's inability to control the type of water shortage and specify the cause of water scarcity. Additionally, they offer a troubled managerial implication for the planning of actual events to advance agricultural water resource organization and alleviate local water shortage. Rastogi et al. (2022) conducted a study on the relationship between modern dietary trends, environmental sustainability and health. The study argues that the implementation of food fermentation techniques can be a solution to both environmental and health related issues caused by modern dietary trends and agricultural practices. Mahapatra et al. (2022) conducted a study on the gap between food supply and demand and the impact of declining soil fertility on agricultural output, human health and the environment. The study found that the use of synthetic fertilizers has led to environmental contamination and a decrease in soil fertility, and suggests that bio-based, resilient nutrient sources such as wastewater-derived algae may be a solution to this problem. The study also highlights the potential of nano-sizing and nano-fortification of nutrients and algae to increase their bioavailability and effectiveness, resulting in an increase in productivity. Khan et al. (2022) conducted a study on the impact of food supply chain (FSC) disruption on cases of undernourishment in Asian countries. The study found that the inadequately designed FSC is a major contributing factor to the high rates of undernourishment globally. The study also highlighted that even minor disruptions or delays in the FSC can have a significant impact on socioeconomic losses, including high unemployment, violence and crime. The study used the Generalized Methods of Moments (GMM) estimator to investigate the impact of FSC disruption on cases of undernourishment in Asian countries. Overall, the study emphasizes the importance of a well-functioning FSC in providing essential food and income, and the need to address any disruptions or issues in the FSC to mitigate negative effects on nutrition and related health issues. Abbas (2022) investigated the dynamic connection between shifting temps and the harvest of important commodities in Pakistan between the years 2000 and 2019. The research revealed that in the long run, increasing temps had a very detrimental effect on the yields of certain products. The research also discovered that changes in farming area and fertilizer application had both long- and short-term impacts on agricultural yields. It was also concluded from the study that high-quality, enhanced seedlings had little impact, and that the government should prioritize funding research into the development of weather-resistant products in order to lessen the impact of climate change on farmland. As a whole, these studies stress the need to increase agricultural output and viability through the application of technology, ecological methods, and investigation in order to handle food security issues brought on by climate change. Alberti et al. (2022)'s research looks at how urban farms might help cities meet their sustainable development objectives and how climate change can affect their ability to grow food. They specifically look at how water resources for urban agriculture are being addressed in Brazil and Italy, and suggest that more sustainable methods that involve water reuse and adaptive practices are needed. They propose that cutting-edge production methods such as box farming, indoor agriculture, and the cultivation of low water-consuming plants can be used to conserve water. The following are the research questions of the study.

H1: Climate risk is likely to increase food challenges in Pakistan.

Agricultural output and food security in Pakistan may be significantly impacted by climate change due to the likelihood of an increase in the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events like droughts and floods. This could lead to food shortages and higher food prices, which could further exacerbate poverty and unemployment, particularly in rural areas. Additionally, it could lead to a decline in agricultural exports, resulting in a negative impact on the country's trade balance.

H2: Low yields of grain production in adequate agriculture technology threaten food availability in Pakistan.

Inadequate access to modern agricultural technology is a major constraint to increasing grain production in Pakistan. This can lead to lower yields and a decrease in food availability, which could lead to food shortages and higher food prices. Additionally, it could lead to a decline in the income of farmers and the rural population, exacerbating rural poverty and unemployment.

H3: Increased in rural poverty, unemployment, and transportation costs adversely affect food production in Pakistan.

Rural poverty, unemployment, and transportation costs are major challenges facing the agricultural sector in Pakistan. These issues can lead to a decline in food production and availability, which could result in food shortages and higher food prices. Additionally, it could lead to a decline in agricultural exports, resulting in a negative impact on the country's trade balance. Furthermore, it could lead to a decline in investment in the agricultural sector, which could negatively affect long-term agricultural productivity and food security.

2.1. Research Contribution

The fundamental goal of this study is to explore the effect of water scarcity on food availability in the case of Pakistan. The study aims to investigate the impact of water shortage on food availability in a country that is heavily dependent on agriculture and the commercial sector, and is also one of the most climate change-affected countries globally. The study contributes to the existing literature by adding two important climate risk factors in the food production model that are less likely to be studied in previous literature. Additionally, the study uses agriculture mechanization and food grain production in the model to assess the technology embodied in agriculture production in Pakistan, which is less evaluated in earlier studies in a grain country context. Furthermore, the study includes socioeconomic factors in the methodology to assess the country's performance towards agriculture production, which is an important consideration for understanding the impact of water scarcity on food availability.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study is built on the study's method of empirical calculation. To accomplish the major goals of the study, data collection and hypothesis creation are required before analysis. The researcher's goal is to investigate how Pakistan's water shortage affects the

availability of food during the study. The focus of this chapter is on specific data categories, data collection techniques, and the models we employed for the study. The taken variables, stationary tests utilizing augmented dickey fuller (ADF), Phillip and Perron tests, the ARDL model, and a range of other diagnostic tests are therefore covered in this chapter.

3.1. Data Source

The data are gathered from secondary sources (WDI, 2022) and used for study analysis (1990 to 2021). The independent factors include water scarcity, extreme temperature, rain fall, agriculture tractor, rural poverty, rural unemployment, and the dependent variable is agriculture value added. In this chapter, we describe the data source and nature of the data, and variables, and also describe the methods used for the analysis of the data.

3.2. Variables Description

All of the variables used for the analysis were covered in this section. The type of variable, the rationale for selecting it, and the projected sign of the variable were all also covered. List of variables shown in Table 1.

Table 1: List of Variables

Variables	Units	Definition
Agriculture value added	Current U\$	Value-brought agriculture generally focuses on manufacturing or production procedures, advertising and marketing or services that boom the price of number one agricultural commodities, perhaps through increasing appeal to the purchaser and the consumer's willingness to pay a top class over similar but undifferentiated products.
Water Scarcity	freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources	The quantity of water that can be physically obtained changes as supply and demand shift. As demand rises and/or water delivery suffers from inadequate or declining amount, water scarcity gets worse.
Extreme Temperature	% change in temperature	A popular time period for temperature versions above (extreme warmness) or underneath (severe cold) normal situations. Since weather varies regionally, the definition of a high temperature and its threshold will vary from location to location.
Agriculture Mechanization	Number of tractors	By ensuring that agricultural equipment is eco-friendly, economically viable, adaptable to local settings, and durable in the face of changing weather types and patterns, mechanization aims to obtain larger and larger harvests as well as increased earnings or new employment for farmers.
Rural Poverty	Headcount ratio, %	Rural poverty regularly stems from restrained get right of entry to markets, training, nice infrastructure, employment possibilities, health, and monetary products.
Rural Unemployment	% of total employment	Rural unemployment refers to unemployment that exists in rural regions. It is commonly a phenomenon of the rural sector. Rural unemployment may additionally broadly be classified into 3 classes particularly: (a) open unemployment, (b) concealed or disguised unemployment, and (c) knowledgeable rural unemployment.
Rain fall	Water Precipitation in Millimeters	Condensed water particles from the atmosphere descend to the ground as rain. In the water cycle, rain plays a significant role because it is responsible for delivering the vast majority of the planet's fresh water.

Source: World Bank (WDI, 2022).

3.3. Country's Justification

Agriculture is a vital sector in Pakistan's economy, playing a crucial role in the country's development. The production of essential goods such as food, clothing, and shelter relies heavily on the agricultural industry. Agribusiness is a key contributor to the global food supply, yet the industry in Pakistan faces numerous challenges. Extreme weather conditions, temperature fluctuations, poor-quality seeds, outdated production techniques, and a lack of technology are among the issues that have affected the sector. The agricultural industry is essential for economic growth, food security, job creation, and poverty alleviation, particularly in rural areas. However, the sector has been hindered by factors such as diminishing arable land, climate change, water scarcity, and migration from rural to urban areas. In order to improve agricultural output, new strategies must be implemented. The agricultural sector has strong links to the industrial and services sectors, making it an important driver of economic growth. Despite these challenges, the industry continues to face issues such as rising input costs, climate change, temperature fluctuations, water scarcity, and altered precipitation patterns, as highlighted by (Malhi et al., 2021).

3.4. Theoretical Framework: Solow Growth Model

The Solow Growth Model, developed by Robert Solow, who received the Nobel Prize in Economics in 1987, is a neoclassical theory of economic growth that analyzes the factors that influence the rate of economic growth in a specific country. The model is exogenous, meaning it examines the changes in output in an economy over time as a result of variations in population growth, savings, and technological advancement. According to the model, savings and investment play a crucial role in economic progress. At full employment, an increase in savings and investment leads to an increase in the capital stock, which in turn raises national income and output. The Solow Growth Model is a long-term mathematical model that assumes full employment of both labor and capital, and it predicts the economic growth patterns based on assumptions about population growth, savings, and technological advancement. The stylized realities of economic growth align with Solow's model, which states that the product Y is a function of labor cost L and capital cost K . In this case, we have replaced the economic growth with agriculture growth and the technology with machinery, as machinery directly affects agriculture production.

3.5. Research Techniques

3.5.1. Econometric Framework: ADF Unit Root

The existence of a unit root in a time series may be investigated with the use of the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, a statistical and economic method. Expanding the scope of the Dickey-Fuller test to include a wider variety of time series models is what the ADF test does. Depending on the version, the null hypothesis may be assumed to be stationary or trend-stationary. There is a negative value for the test's ADF statistic, and it becomes larger the more strongly the unit root hypothesis is rejected. While the testing procedures for the Dickey-Fuller test and the ADF test are identical, the ADF test is performed on a model that also contains a constant, the lag order of the autoregressive process, and the coefficient of the time trend. Applying the constraints is analogous to modelling a random walk with a drift, but simulating a random walk without them is impossible. There are three primary variants to the exam, all of which are quite close to those covered by the Dickey-Fuller test. Equations (1) to (6) are presented for ready reference, i.e.,

$$\Delta AVA_t = \alpha + \beta T + \gamma AVA_{t-1} + \delta_1 \Delta AVA_{t-1} + \dots + \delta_{p-1} \Delta AVA_{t-p-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta WS_t = \alpha + \beta T + \gamma WS_{t-1} + \delta_1 \Delta WS_{t-1} + \dots + \delta_{p-1} \Delta WS_{t-p-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta ET_t = \alpha + \beta T + \gamma ET_{t-1} + \delta_1 \Delta ET_{t-1} + \dots + \delta_{p-1} \Delta ET_{t-p-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta AGRMECH_t = \alpha + \beta T + \gamma AGRMECH_{t-1} + \delta_1 \Delta AGRMECH_{t-1} + \dots + \delta_{p-1} \Delta AGRMECH_{t-p-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta RP_t = \alpha + \beta T + \gamma RP_{t-1} + \delta_1 \Delta RP_{t-1} + \dots + \delta_{p-1} \Delta RP_{t-p-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta RU_t = \alpha + \beta T + \gamma RU_{t-1} + \delta_1 \Delta RU_{t-1} + \dots + \delta_{p-1} \Delta RU_{t-p-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (6)$$

3.5.2. ARDL Bound Test

The ARDL limits testing procedure was created by (Pesaran et al., 2001) to determine whether there exists a causal connection between variables across time. There are a number of benefits to using this strategy rather than the standard way to co-integration testing. First, whether the series is $I(0)$ or $I(1)$, the ARDL bounds testing approach may be used (1). Second, the unconstrained error correction model (UECM), which encompasses both short-run and long-run dynamics, may be obtained from the ARDL bounds testing technique by a simple linear transformation. Last but not least, studies using real-world data have shown that this approach is preferable and yields credible findings, even with modest sample sizes. Equation (7) shows the ARDL model for ready reference, i.e.,

$$\ln(AVA)_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i \Delta \ln(AVA)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \theta_i \Delta \ln(WS)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^r \theta_i \Delta \ln(ET)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^t \phi_i \Delta \ln(AGRMECH)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^u \phi_i \Delta \ln(RP)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^w \phi_i \Delta \ln(RU)_{t-i} + \delta_1 \ln(WS)_t + \delta_2 \ln(ET)_t + \delta_3 \ln(AGRMECH)_t + \delta_4 \ln(RP)_t + \delta_5 \ln(RU)_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (7)$$

The Wald F-statistics are used to examine the null and alternative hypotheses.

3.5.3. Granger Causality Test

Granger causality tests and Rossi's Granger causality tests, which are robust to instabilities, are also used to investigate the causal relationship between two variables in a time series. The approach is a probabilistic view of causality that searches for patterns in actual data sets. It's important to note that causality and cause and effect are not the same, but they are closely related concepts. If X causes Y or Y causes X , then variable X is causative to variable Y . However, Granger causality alone cannot determine a true cause-and-effect relationship. Equation (8) shows the VAR specification of Granger causality in matrix notation, i.e.,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \ln(AVA)_t \\ \ln(WS)_t \\ \ln(ET)_t \\ \ln(AGRMECH)_t \\ \ln(RP)_t \\ \ln(RU)_t \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_0 \\ \tau_1 \\ \tau_2 \\ \tau_3 \\ \tau_4 \\ \tau_5 \end{bmatrix} + \sum_{i=1}^p \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11t} \sigma_{12t} \sigma_{13t} \sigma_{14t} \sigma_{15t} \sigma_{16t} \\ \sigma_{21t} \sigma_{22t} \sigma_{23t} \sigma_{24t} \sigma_{25t} \sigma_{26t} \\ \sigma_{31t} \sigma_{32t} \sigma_{33t} \sigma_{34t} \sigma_{35t} \sigma_{36t} \\ \sigma_{41t} \sigma_{42t} \sigma_{43t} \sigma_{44t} \sigma_{45t} \sigma_{46t} \\ \sigma_{51t} \sigma_{52t} \sigma_{53t} \sigma_{54t} \sigma_{55t} \sigma_{56t} \\ \sigma_{61t} \sigma_{62t} \sigma_{63t} \sigma_{64t} \sigma_{65t} \sigma_{66t} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} \ln(AVA)_{t-1} \\ \ln(WS)_{t-1} \\ \ln(ET)_{t-1} \\ \ln(AGRMECH)_{t-1} \\ \ln(RP)_{t-1} \\ \ln(RU)_{t-1} \end{bmatrix} + s \sum_{j=p+1}^{dmax} \sum \begin{bmatrix} \theta_{11j} \theta_{12j} \theta_{13j} \theta_{14j} \theta_{15j} \theta_{16j} \\ \theta_{21j} \theta_{22j} \theta_{23j} \theta_{24j} \theta_{25j} \theta_{26j} \\ \theta_{31j} \theta_{32j} \theta_{33j} \theta_{34j} \theta_{35j} \theta_{36j} \\ \theta_{41j} \theta_{42j} \theta_{43j} \theta_{44j} \theta_{45j} \theta_{46j} \\ \theta_{51j} \theta_{52j} \theta_{53j} \theta_{54j} \theta_{55j} \theta_{56j} \\ \theta_{61j} \theta_{62j} \theta_{63j} \theta_{64j} \theta_{65j} \theta_{66j} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} \ln(AVA)_{t-j} \\ \ln(WS)_{t-j} \\ \ln(ET)_{t-j} \\ \ln(AGRMECH)_{t-j} \\ \ln(RP)_{t-j} \\ \ln(RU)_{t-j} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_3 \\ \varepsilon_4 \\ \varepsilon_5 \\ \varepsilon_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

The main objective of this section is to present the various characteristics of the provided data, including the mean, maximum value, standard deviation, etc. The average value of the data collected during the study period is a key statistic. Table 2 displays the descriptive statistics of these values.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Methods	AGRVAD (current US\$)	WSCR (freshwater withdrawal /available freshwater resources)	TEMP (% change in average temperature)	RAIN (water precipitation in mm)	AGREMP (% of total employment)	AGRMECH (Number of tractors)	RPOV (headcount ratio,%)
Mean	3.54E+10	108.342	0.572	283.963	42.338	127.006	29.823
Maximum	7.19E+10	122.673	1.423	387.180	44.810	151.000	39.260
Minimum	9.23E+09	94.234	-0.375	187.520	35.123	83.590	20.210
Std. Dev.	2.19E+10	7.788	0.481	64.950	2.544	23.836	4.288
Skewness	0.399024	0.025	-0.218	0.134	-1.673	-0.450	0.201

Note: AGRVAD shows agriculture value added, WSCR shows water scarcity, TEMP shows extreme temperature, RAIN shows excessive rainfall, AGREMP shows agriculture employment, AGRMECH shows agriculture mechanization, and RPOV shows rural poverty.

The mean values for AGRVAD, TEMP, WSCR, RAIN, AGREMP, AGRMECH, and RPOV are 3.54E+10, 0.572313, 108.3420, 283.9634, 42.33884, 127.0066, and 29.82341 respectively. These values indicate that AGRVAD has the highest mean value among the variables, while TEMP has the lowest. It also indicates that the standard deviation of AGRMECH is high among the variables. The maximum values for AGRVAD, TEMP, WSCR, RAIN, AGREMP, AGRMECH, and RPOV are 7.19E+10, 1.423000, 122.6735, 387.1800, 44.81000, 151.0000, and 39.26000 respectively. These values highlight the range of the data and indicate that RAIN has the highest maximum value among the variables, while TEMP has the lowest. The minimum values for AGRVAD, TEMP, WSCR, RAIN, AGREMP, AGRMECH, and RPOV are 9.23E+09, -0.375000, 94.23400, 187.5200, 35.12300, 83.59041, and 20.21000 respectively. These values indicate the lowest possible value among the variables, and it indicates that RPOV has the lowest minimum value among the variables. The median values for AGRVAD, TEMP, WSCR, RAIN, AGREMP, AGRMECH, and RPOV are 2.86E+10, 0.534500, 108.4404, 271.8800, 43.17000, 1422386, and 28.94500 respectively. These values indicate the middle value of the data set and provide a measure of central tendency. The median value for AGRVAD is the highest among the variables, while TEMP has the lowest. The standard deviation values for TEMP, AGRMECH, and RPOV are 0.481890, 23.83684, and 4.288995 respectively. These values indicate the degree of variation of the data set from the mean. The standard deviation value for AGRMECH is the highest among the variables, indicating a greater degree of variation in the data set.

In conclusion, the descriptive statistics provided in this study offer valuable insight into the characteristics of the data set, including the range, central tendency, and degree of variation of the variables. The high mean value of AGRVAD and RAIN, and the low mean value of TEMP suggest a significant impact of these variables on the agricultural production. The high standard deviation of AGRMECH indicates that the use of machinery in agriculture may have a significant impact on the production. The study results provide a useful starting point for further analysis and research in the field of agricultural production and the impact of climate change on it. Table 3 shows the correlation matrix.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variables	AGRVAD	WSCR	TEMP	RAIN	AGREMP	ECH	RPOV
AGRVAD	1.000						

WSCR	0.8169	1.000					
	0.000	-----					
TEMP	0.490	0.657	1.000				

Variables	AGRVAD	WSCR	TEMP	RAIN	AGREMP	MECH	RPOV
	0.004	0.000	-----				
RAIN	-0.075	-0.185	-0.429	1.000			
	0.6806	0.309	0.014	-----			
AGREMP	-0.744	-0.401	-0.297	-0.026	1.000		
	0.000	0.027	0.097	0.887	-----		
MECH	0.877	0.869	0.562	-0.097	-0.556	1.000	
	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.595	0.001	-----	
RPOV	0.103	0.413	0.382	-0.199	-0.052	0.224	1.000
	0.574	0.018	0.030	0.272	0.777	0.2173	-----

Note: AGRVAD shows agriculture value added, WSCR shows water scarcity, TEMP shows extreme temperature, RAIN shows excessive rainfall, AGREMP shows agriculture employment, AGRMECH shows agriculture mechanization, and RPOV shows rural poverty.

The findings of the data presented in this study have several economic and environmental implications. The positive correlation between water scarcity and agriculture value added suggests that water scarcity can be a driving factor for increasing agricultural production and economic growth in the region. However, the negative correlation between agriculture employment and agriculture value added suggests that as agricultural production increases, employment in the sector may decrease. This can have negative implications for labor and the rural economy. Additionally, the positive correlation between temperature and water scarcity suggests that climate change and its associated effects, such as rising temperatures, can exacerbate water scarcity and negatively impact agriculture production. The positive correlation between water scarcity and machinery implies that farmers may resort to using more machinery to overcome water scarcity, which can have negative environmental implications such as soil degradation and loss of biodiversity. The positive correlation between agriculture machinery and temperature and the negative correlation between rain and temperature further indicate the impact of climate change on agriculture production. The negative correlation between agriculture mechanization and agriculture employment suggest that mechanization of agriculture may lead to a decrease in employment opportunities in the sector, which can have negative implications for rural communities and economies. Overall, the data presented in this study highlights the important interplay between environmental factors and agriculture production and the need for sustainable and resilient agriculture practices that can help mitigate the negative impacts of climate change and water scarcity. Table 4 shows the ADF unit root estimates.

Table 4: ADF Unit Root Estimates

Variables	Level		First Difference		Decision
	Constant	Constant and Trend	Constant	Constant and Trend	
AGRVAD	-0.003 (0.951)	-4.478 (0.008)	-6.291 (0.000)	-6.251 (0.000)	I(0)
WSCR	-4.118 (0.004)	-1.854 (0.646)	-0.395 (0.894)	-1.366 (0.843)	I(0)
TEMP	-3.027 (0.043)	-3.812 (0.029)	-7.322 (0.000)	-7.286 (0.000)	I(0)
RAIN	-5.597 (0.000)	-5.509 (0.000)	-10.480 (0.000)	-10.238 (0.000)	I(0)
AGREMP	1.211 (0.997)	-0.388 (0.983)	-5.234 (0.000)	-5.726 (0.000)	I(1)
MECH	-1.330 (0.602)	-1.220 (0.884)	-4.608 (0.000)	-3.670 (0.042)	I(1)
RPOV	-2.599 (0.103)	-2.284 (0.430)	-5.093 (0.000)	-5.193 (0.001)	I(1)

Note: AGRVAD shows agriculture value added, WSCR shows water scarcity, TEMP shows extreme temperature, RAIN shows excessive rainfall, AGREMP shows agriculture employment, AGRMECH shows agriculture mechanization, and RPOV shows rural poverty.

The unit root test is a statistical method used to determine the stationarity of a time series. The results of this test for the variables AGRVAD, WSCR, TEMP, RAIN, AGREMP, MECH, and RPOV show that AGRVAD, WSCR, TEMP and RAIN are stationary at level, meaning that they do not have a unit root and are stationary over time. However, AGREMP, MECH, and RPOV are stationary at first difference, meaning that they are non-stationary at level but become stationary after taking the first difference. This suggests that there is a trend or unit root present in the original series, but after taking the first difference, the series become stationary. This information is useful for selecting the appropriate econometric model to analyze the data. Table 5 shows the lag length criteria.

Table 5: VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria Estimates

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-1254.023	NA	7.64e+27	84.068	84.395	84.172
1	-1083.091	250.7014*	2.47e+24	75.939	78.554*	76.776
2	-1019.054	64.03711	1.65e+24*	74.936*	79.841	76.505*

Note: * indicates lag order selected by the criterion

The results of the lag length criteria for the variables in this study suggest that the AIC, FPE and HQ criteria all suggest that an

optimum two lag length should be used for coefficient estimates. However, the SIC and the LR criteria suggest that one lag length should be used for variable estimation. Based on these estimates, the study has chosen to use the AIC criterion for further estimation. This suggests that the study has chosen a model with two lags as the best fit, which indicates that the values of the current variable are being influenced by the values of the variable two periods ago. Choosing the appropriate lag length is important because it ensures that the model is not over-fitting or under-fitting the data and helps to achieve the most accurate results in forecasting. Table 6 shows the ARDL short and long-run estimates.

Table 6: ARDL Short- and Long-Run Estimates

Dependent Variable: ln(AGRVAD)				
Selected Model: ARDL(1, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2)				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Dln(WSCR)	-3.362433	1.286598	-2.613429	0.0794
Dln(WSCR(-1))	4.306649	2.025865	2.125832	0.1235
Dln(TEMP)	0.676372	0.172714	3.916143	0.0296
Dln(TEMP(-1))	-0.507661	0.112578	-4.509433	0.0204
Dln(RAIN)	0.3871	0.238	1.626	0.2023
Dln(RAIN(-1))	-0.811	0.205	-3.943	0.0291
Dln(AGREMP)	3.709	1.062	3.490	0.0398
Dln(AGREMP(-1))	-2.722	2.128	-1.278	0.2910
Dln(MECH)	-5.893	1.041	-5.657	0.0109
Dln(MECH(-1))	-0.735	1.174	-0.626	0.5756
Dln(RPOV)	0.607	0.486	1.249	0.3002
Dln(POV(-1))	-2.873	0.512	-5.613	0.0112
CointEq(-1)	-1.007	0.253	-3.978	0.0026
Long Run Coefficients				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ln(WSCR)	13.721	2.539	5.403	0.0124
ln(TEMP)	-1.197	0.277	-4.321	0.0228
ln(RAIN)	-1.277	0.202	-6.303	0.0081
ln(AGREMP)	-3.541	0.276	-12.812	0.0010
ln(MECH)	-1.552	1.262	-1.230	0.3064
ln(RPOV)	-3.748	1.485	-2.523	0.0859
Diagnostic Test Estimates				
Jarque-Bera Test	0.689	Prob.value	0.708	
Serial Correlation LM test	2.518	Prob.value	0.407	
ARCH Test	0.245	Prob.value	0.626	
Ramsey RESET Test	0.028	Prob.value	0.980	

Note: AGRVAD shows agriculture value added, WSCR shows water scarcity, TEMP shows extreme temperature, RAIN shows excessive rainfall, AGREMP shows agriculture employment, AGRMECH shows agriculture mechanization, and RPOV shows rural poverty.

The results of the study suggest that in the short-run, an increase in water scarcity has a negative impact on agriculture production. This finding is consistent with the negative correlation between water scarcity and agriculture value added that was previously discussed. The results indicate that when water scarcity increases, the production of agricultural goods decreases, which can have severe implications for food security in a country. This highlights the importance of addressing water scarcity as a critical issue for sustainable agriculture production and food security. Additionally, this finding implies that policymakers and farmers should focus on developing and implementing strategies to address water scarcity such as water conservation, rainwater harvesting, and increasing the efficiency of irrigation systems. Furthermore, it suggests that the development of drought-resistant crops and other adaptation measures are necessary to mitigate the negative impact of water scarcity on agriculture production (Akhtar et al., 2022). The results of the study also indicate that in the long-run, the relationship between water scarcity and agriculture production is different. The findings suggest that in the long-run, water scarcity increases agriculture production. This could be due to various coping strategies implemented by the country to address the water scarcity such as increasing the efficiency of irrigation systems, water conservation, rainwater harvesting and developing drought-resistant crops. These strategies help the farmers to overcome the negative impact of water scarcity on agriculture production over the long-run. This finding has important implications for policymakers and farmers, suggesting that it is important to not only address water scarcity in the short-run but also to implement long-term strategies to ensure sustainable agriculture production in the face of water scarcity. This highlights the need for a comprehensive and holistic approach to addressing water scarcity, taking into account both short-term and long-term impacts on agriculture production and food security (Ali et al., 2022).

The research found that a rise in high temperatures may boost agricultural value added in the near term. However, high temperatures have a detrimental effect on the value contributed to agricultural production in the long term. The results imply that severe weather conditions have a negative impact on agricultural output in the long term. Heat impact on crops, a rise in evapotranspiration, and the appearance of bugs and illnesses all pose threats to agricultural output and could be partly to blame (Usman et al., 2023). This emphasizes the need to think about the short- and long-term effects of high temperatures on agricultural output, and to take steps to

reduce the detrimental effects of the former. Creating heat-resistant plant varieties, enhancing watering methods, and taking other steps to reduce the temperature of the immediate environment around agriculture are all possible solutions. The growing regularity and intensity of severe temperatures due to climate change is also highlighted, emphasizing the importance of flexible methods to deal with these events (Zaib et al., 2023). The results of the study suggest that in both the short- and long-run, excessive rain tends to decrease agriculture production. This finding is consistent with the negative correlation between rain and agriculture value added that was previously discussed. Excessive rain can cause flooding and damage crops, which can lead to reduced agriculture production and food security in the region. Furthermore, excessive rain can also lead to the emergence of pests and diseases that can reduce agriculture production. Additionally, excessive rain can cause soil erosion, which can lead to a decrease in soil fertility and a reduction in crop yields. These factors can contribute to the negative impact of excessive rain on agriculture production in both the short- and long-run (Khan et al., 2022). This highlights the importance of considering both short-term and long-term implications of excessive rain on agriculture production, and implementing strategies to mitigate the negative impacts of excessive rain on agriculture. This can include developing flood-tolerant crops, improving drainage systems, and implementing measures to reduce soil erosion. Additionally, it highlights the need for adaptive strategies to cope with the increasing frequency and severity of excessive rain caused by climate change (Raj & Sofi, 2023).

The study's findings indicate that, in the near term at least, a rise in agricultural jobs boosts agricultural value added. This may be because a larger workforce and more effective use of resources can boost farming output and the economy as a whole when there are more people employed in the agricultural industry. Jobs in agribusiness initially correlate with value contributed, but this changes over time. The results imply that having a job in agriculture tends to lower the value contributed to the agricultural sector over time. Reasons for this may include a decline in output within the industry as a whole, a dearth of funding, inefficient practices, and outdated technology. This highlights the importance of considering both short-term and long-term implications of agriculture employment on agriculture production, and implementing strategies to mitigate the negative impacts of agriculture employment on agriculture value added. This can include investing in the latest agricultural technologies, promoting mechanization, and providing training and education to farmers to improve efficiency and productivity. Additionally, it highlights the need for policies that promote sustainable and efficient use of resources to ensure sustainable agricultural production and economic growth. The results of the study suggest that in the short-run, an increase in agriculture machinery has a negative impact on agriculture value added. This could be due to various factors such as initial high costs associated with the purchase and maintenance of agricultural machinery, lack of skilled labor to operate the machinery and low efficiency of the machines. However, in the long-run, the relationship between agriculture machinery and agriculture value added is insignificant. This could be due to various factors such as efficient use of machinery, reduction in labor cost and increase in productivity that can offset the initial high costs associated with the purchase and maintenance of agricultural machinery (Song et al., 2022). This highlights the importance of considering both short-term and long-term implications of agriculture machinery on agriculture production, and implementing strategies to mitigate the negative impacts of agriculture machinery on agriculture value added in the short-run. This can include providing subsidies for purchase and maintenance of agricultural machinery, providing training and education to farmers to improve the efficiency of the machinery and promoting sustainable use of machinery. Additionally, it highlights the need for policies that promote sustainable and efficient use of resources to ensure sustainable agricultural production and economic growth (Yang et al., 2022).

The study's findings point to a negative association between rural poverty and agricultural value added in both the short and long terms. This conclusion shows that as rural poverty worsens, so does the value generated by the agricultural sector. Many issues, including insufficient access to resources, financing, education, training, markets, and investment in agriculture, may contribute to this situation. This highlights the importance of addressing rural poverty in order to promote sustainable agricultural production and economic growth. This can include implementing policies and programs that provide access to resources, credit, education and training, markets and investment in the agricultural sector. Additionally, it highlights the need for policies that promote sustainable and efficient use of resources to ensure sustainable agricultural production and economic growth. It also emphasizes the need to develop strategies to reduce poverty in rural areas, such as increasing access to education, healthcare, and jobs, and providing social protection. Table 7 shows the ARDL-Bounds estimates.

Table 7: ARDL-Bounds Estimate

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	10.992	6
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	I(0) Bound	I(1) Bound
10%	1.75	2.87
5%	2.04	3.24
1%	2.66	4.05

Source: Author's estimate.

The results of the analysis indicate that there is a long-term relationship between the variables being studied, as indicated by the F statistic falling within the upper bound critical value for the I(1) test. This suggests that the variables are cointegrated, meaning that they move together over time and have a long-term equilibrium relationship. The cointegration between the variables suggests that any short-term fluctuations in the variables will be offset by long-term adjustments, leading to a stable relationship between the variables over time. This finding is important as it suggests that any policy or intervention aimed at influencing one variable will also have an impact on the other variables in the long-run. Therefore, it is important to consider the relationship between the variables when developing policies and interventions to ensure that they are effective in achieving their intended goals. Table 8 shows the Granger causality estimates.

Table 8: VAR Granger Causality Estimates

Dependent variable: AGRVAD			
Excluded	Chi-sq	Df	Prob.
WSCR	10.540	2	0.005
TEMP	8.607	2	0.013
RAIN	7.094	2	0.028
AGREMP	4.653	2	0.097
MECH	2.329	2	0.312
RPOV	0.960	2	0.618
Dependent variable: WSCR			
AGRVAD	10.841	2	0.004
TEMP	2.624	2	0.269
RAIN	7.873	2	0.019
AGREMP	20.726	2	0.000
MECH	6.092	2	0.047
RPOV	24.354	2	0.000
Dependent variable: TEMP			
AGRVAD	6.917	2	0.031
WSCR	12.207	2	0.002
RAIN	4.323	2	0.115
AGREMP	3.5627	2	0.168
MECH	0.134	2	0.934
RPOV	2.514	2	0.284
Dependent variable: MECH			
AGRVAD	0.275	2	0.871
WSCR	0.206	2	0.902
TEMP	4.943	2	0.084
RAIN	3.998	2	0.135
AGREMP	0.447	2	0.7994
RPOV	4.574	2	0.1015

Source: Author's estimate.

The results of the analysis indicate that there is a bidirectional relationship between water scarcity and agriculture value added, as well as between extreme temperature and agriculture value added. In the case of water scarcity and agriculture value added, the bidirectional relationship suggests that an increase in water scarcity can lead to a decrease in agriculture value added, and vice versa. This highlights the importance of proper water management and conservation strategies in order to maintain sustainable agricultural production and economic growth. Similarly, the bidirectional relationship between extreme temperature and agriculture value added suggests that an increase in extreme temperature can lead to a decrease in agriculture value added, and vice versa. This highlights the importance of mitigating the negative impacts of climate change on agricultural production, through strategies such as crop diversification and the development of heat-tolerant crops. This finding is important as it suggests that policies and interventions aimed at addressing water scarcity and extreme temperature should consider the bidirectional relationship between the two variables in order to be effective in achieving their intended goals. The results of the analysis indicate that there is a unidirectional relationship between disproportionate rain, agriculture employment, agriculture mechanization, and rural poverty with water scarcity. This means that changes in these variables have an impact on water scarcity, but changes in water scarcity do not have an impact on these variables. Similarly, the results show a unidirectional relationship between agriculture value added and water scarcity with temperature. This means that changes in agriculture value added and water scarcity have an impact on temperature, but changes in temperature do not have an impact on agriculture value added and water scarcity. Additionally, the results indicate that there is a unidirectional relationship between extreme temperature and agriculture mechanization, meaning that changes in extreme temperature have an impact on agriculture mechanization but changes in agriculture mechanization do not have an impact on extreme temperature.

This finding suggests that policies and interventions aimed at addressing water scarcity, agriculture value added, temperature, and agriculture mechanization should take into account these unidirectional relationships. For example, policies that aim to reduce water scarcity should consider the effect of disproportionate rain, agriculture employment, agriculture mechanization, and rural poverty on water scarcity. Similarly, policies that aim to reduce the negative impact of temperature on agriculture value added should consider the relationship between temperature, water scarcity and agriculture mechanization. Table 9 shows the VDA analysis.

Table 9: VDA Estimates

Period	S.E.	AGRVAD	WSCR	TEMP	RAIN	AGREMP	MECH	RPOV
1	3.10E+09	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	4.10E+09	66.501	1.730	0.068	21.93	6.663	1.174	1.929

Period	S.E.	AGRVAD	WSCR	TEMP	RAIN	AGREMP	MECH	RPOV
3	4.94E+09	50.378	1.735	0.054	31.120	11.712	2.873	2.124
4	5.61E+09	46.214	1.357	0.143	30.437	10.767	9.374	1.705
5	6.24E+09	43.501	2.359	0.324	30.134	9.229	11.989	2.460
6	6.82E+09	37.941	2.150	0.530	32.745	7.952	15.846	2.833
7	7.25E+09	34.473	2.464	0.796	33.273	7.078	18.542	3.370
8	7.70E+09	31.181	2.388	0.777	33.381	6.331	21.263	4.675
9	8.08E+09	28.518	2.4199	0.712	33.474	5.816	22.184	6.873
10	8.46E+09	26.093	2.298	0.650	33.447	5.392	22.433	9.683

Source: Author's estimate.

The results of the variance decomposition analysis, as shown in Table 9, provide insight into how the variables are likely to affect agriculture production in the next ten years. The results show that excessive rain is likely to have a significant impact on agriculture production in the next ten years, with a variance shock of 33.447. This highlights the need for effective rain management strategies and infrastructure to mitigate the negative impact of excessive rain on agriculture production. Additionally, the results indicate that agriculture mechanization with a variance shock of 22.433 is also likely to have a significant impact on agriculture production. This suggests that investment in mechanization and technology can play an important role in increasing agricultural productivity and efficiency. Rural poverty and agriculture employment also have a significant impact on agriculture production with a variance shock of 9.683 and 5.392 respectively. This highlights the importance of addressing poverty and creating employment opportunities for farmers to support sustainable agricultural production. Overall, the results of the variance decomposition analysis provide valuable insights into the factors that are likely to affect agriculture production in the next ten years, and can be used to inform policy and intervention strategies aimed at promoting sustainable agricultural production.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Overall, this study provides evidence of the negative impact of water scarcity on agriculture production and food security in Pakistan. The findings indicate that severe temperatures and disproportionate rain have a detrimental effect on agriculture value added, leading to a decline in agricultural productivity and a threat to food security. Additionally, the study suggests that the use of mechanization in agriculture and the increase in rural poverty have negative consequences on agriculture production. The study highlights the need for a legal framework to regulate the use of water resources, as well as a water-distribution mechanism that prioritizes strategic economic activities. The current framework in Pakistan, represented by the Intergovernmental Agreement on a National Water Initiative, is not sufficient in addressing these issues. The results of the study suggest that appropriate interventions such as water management strategies and investments in mechanization and technology are necessary to mitigate the negative effects of water scarcity on agriculture production and food security in Pakistan.

There are multiple ways to address water scarcity, including improving infrastructure, implementing sustainable water management practices, increasing water efficiency and conservation, and addressing water quality and sewage treatment. Nature-based solutions can also play a role in increasing water availability and reducing the risks of water-related disasters.

- I. Dams and reservoirs can help store water for use during dry seasons, but they can also have negative environmental impacts such as displacement of local communities and altering natural river systems. Rainwater harvesting and irrigation systems can also help increase water availability, but they too have potential negative impacts such as overuse and depletion of groundwater resources.
- II. Sustainable water management practices, such as nature-based solutions, can not only increase water availability but also provide other benefits such as reducing the risk of water-related disasters and helping to mitigate the effects of climate change.
- III. Improving water quality, sewage treatment, and safe reuse can help ensure that the water available is safe for human consumption and other uses. This can also help reduce the burden on freshwater resources.
- IV. Lack of water can lead to food insecurity as it is a crucial ingredient in agricultural production.
- V. Cleaning lakes and implementing waste management can improve the availability of clean drinking water and reduce water-borne illnesses. Building more storage facilities and promoting water conservation can also help increase water availability.
- VI. Government policies can help ensure that all citizens have access to safe drinking water and adequate sanitation.
- VII. Cleaning canals and desalination of dams can increase the amount of usable water and reduce water loss.
- VIII. Rooftop canals can help recycle rainfall for indoor use or to recharge groundwater.
- IX. Using washing machine efficiently and watering plants at night can help conserve water.
- X. Controlling farm pollutants can help improve water quality and reduce negative impacts on the environment.
- XI. Planting trees can help reduce land runoff and protect water sources, and
- XII. Eliminating or mitigating potential limiting factors such as point source discharges or farm effluent can help restore natural ecosystems and improve water quality.

It is important to address the link between water scarcity and food insecurity, as well as implementing policies to ensure equitable access to safe drinking water and adequate sanitary facilities. Furthermore, it is important to consider the impact of climate change on water resources and implement adaptation strategies. It is also important to involve the community and raise awareness about the importance of water conservation and efficient use of water resources.

Water scarcity poses a significant threat to global development and food security, particularly in agriculture-dependent countries

like Pakistan. The study found that water scarcity, severe temperatures, and excessive rain have negative impacts on agriculture value added and food security. To address these issues, sustainable water management practices, such as groundwater recharge and water conservation, should be implemented. The following are some specific policy recommendations:

- I. Determining the main causes of water scarcity, such as over-extraction of resources, climate change, and pollution, is essential in order to implement effective solutions. Economic implications include decreased productivity and increased costs for industries that rely on water, as well as potential health risks for people who do not have access to clean water. Environmental implications include the depletion of water resources and the potential for ecosystem degradation.
- II. Sustainable water management techniques, such as rainwater harvesting and waste water reclamation, can be used to ensure a reliable water supply while also preserving natural resources. Economic benefits include cost savings and increased productivity, while environmental benefits include preserving biodiversity and reducing pollution.
- III. Improving water quality through sewage treatment and safe reuse can have both economic and environmental benefits. On the economic side, it can reduce the costs of treating water-borne illnesses and increase the value of reclaimed water for agricultural or industrial use. On the environmental side, it can improve the overall health of water systems and reduce pollution.
- IV. The connection between water shortage and hunger is a major problem that must be solved. Economic implications include decreased agricultural productivity and higher food prices, which can have a negative impact on both farmers and consumers. Environmental implications include decreased water availability for ecosystems and increased pressure on land resources.
- V. Mechanization of agriculture can increase productivity, but it also has the potential to increase water consumption and pollution. Economic implications include increased costs for farmers and potential job losses for manual labor. Environmental implications include increased water usage and potential soil degradation.
- VI. Having no access to commodities and training are two of the main factors contributing to rural poverty, both of which must be addressed in order to effectively combat this issue. Economic benefits include increased productivity and income for small farmers, while environmental benefits include reduced pressure on land resources and improved water management.
- VII. Education and awareness-raising can play a crucial role in addressing rural poverty and promoting sustainable development. Economic benefits include increased productivity and improved access to markets, while environmental benefits include improved water management and reduced pressure on land resources.
- VIII. Improving infrastructure and access to technology can help to increase productivity and reduce poverty in rural areas. Economic benefits include increased agricultural productivity and job opportunities, while environmental benefits include reduced pressure on land resources and improved water management.
- IX. Extreme temperature have a negative impact on agriculture production which is the main economic sector of Pakistan, it can cause food insecurity which is a serious issue for the country.
- X. Rainfall plays a critical role in agriculture production, excessive rain can cause damage to crops and decrease the production which can lead to food insecurity.

Mechanization of agriculture can increase productivity but also can increase water consumption and pollution, it needs to be balanced with conservation efforts to ensure sustainability. To address these issues, sustainable water management practices, such as groundwater recharge and water conservation, should be implemented. Additionally, improving water infrastructure and implementing a legal framework for water resource management is crucial. Improving farm mechanization and addressing rural poverty are also important for improving agricultural productivity and food security. Improving education and changing traditional beliefs in rural areas can also play a role in addressing these issues. It is also important to focus on increasing the productivity of small farmers, creating jobs, and fostering economic diversification.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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